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RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING ROLI

РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ НА ПУТИ СОКРАЩЕНИЯ ТЕНЕВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ

THE ROLE OF DIGITALIZATION IN REDUCING THE SHADOW ECONOMY

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu maqola milliy iqtisodiyotda yashirin iqtisodiy faoliyat ulushini kamaytirishda raqamlashtirishning roli muhimligini ochib beradi. Tadqiqotda muallifning e‘tibori raqamli transformatsiyaning milliy iqtisodiyotga va davlat ijtimoiy hayotiga ta‘sirini o‘rganishga qaratilgan, shuningdek, raqamlashtirish va yashirin iqtisodiyotning o‘zaro bog‘liqligini regressiv tahlil qilish uchun hisob-kitoblarni taqdim etadi. Raqamlashtirishning bir qator afzalliklari va kamchiliklari SWOT tahlili orqali o‘rganiladi va tahlil qilinadi. Ko‘zlangan maqsad – raqamlashtirishning ahamiyati va uning O‘zbekistonda yashirin iqtisodiyot ulushiga ta‘sirini aniqlash. Foydalanilgan o‘zgaruvchilar Internetdan foydalanuvchilarning soni va Kogon usuli bo‘yicha hisoblangan yashirin iqtisodiyotning ulushidir. Fikrimizcha, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirishning ijobiy ta‘siri milliy iqtisodiyotda soya sektorining ulushini kamaytirishdagi xavflardan ustundir.

Kalit so‘zlar: raqamlashtirish, raqamli iqtisodiyot, raqamli texnologiyalar, Iqtisodiyotning uberizatsiyasi, raqamli yashirin iqtisodiyot, yashirin iqtisodiyot, internet foydalanuvchilari, vektor avtoregressiyasi, SWOT tahlili.

Аннотация

Данная статья раскрывает важность роли цифровизации на пути сокращения доли теневых экономических деятельностей в национальной экономике. В исследовании внимание автора сфокусировано на изучении

влияния цифровой трансформации на экономику в целом и общества в частности приводятся исчисления регрессионного анализа взаимозависимости цифровизации и теневой экономики. Анализируется ряд преимуществ и недостатков цифровизации посредством SWOT-анализа. Целью статьи является выявление значимости цифровизации и её влияния на долю теневой экономики в Узбекистане. В качестве переменных используются количество интернет-пользователей и доля теневой экономики, оцененная методом Кагана. На наш взгляд положительное влияние цифровизации экономики превалирует над его рисками на пути сокращения доли теневого сектора в национальной экономике.

Ключевые слова: цифровизация, цифровая экономика, цифровые технологии, убризация экономики, цифровая теневая экономика, теневая экономика, интернет-пользователи, векторная авторегрессия, SWOT-анализ.

Abstract

This article reveals the importance of the role of digitalization in reducing the share of shadow economic activities in the national economy. In the study, the author's attention is focused on studying the impact of digital transformation on the economy as a whole and the social life of the state, and also provides calculations for a regression analysis of the interdependence of digitalization and the shadow economy. A number of advantages and disadvantages of digitalization are explored and analyzed through SWOT analysis. The main goal is to identify the significance of digitalization and its impact on the share of the shadow economy in Uzbekistan. The variables used are the number of Internet users and the share of the shadow economy, estimated by the Kagan method. The central takeaway from our review is that the positive impact of economic digitalization outweighs its risks in reducing the share of the shadow sector in the national economy.

Keywords: digitalization, digital economy, digital technologies, Uberization of the economy, digital shadow economy, shadow economy, Internet users, vector autoregression, SWOT analysis.

Introduction

During the period of development of modern technologies and innovations, digitalization is taken for granted and necessary for economic development. The blurring boundaries of the digital and traditional worlds are being integrated into advanced technologies and systemic innovations as technological changes permeate all aspects of socio-economic activities in the national economy. React competently and at all levels: public, state and personal. The presence of technology and digitalization in general, as well as actions and machinations in the digital world and the rapid growth of their number, forms the definition of the digital shadow economy. Aspects of this phenomenon are very diverse. According to the definition of prevailing academic economists, there is one common feature of the shadow economy - it is any undocumented activity. It is this type of action that can be carried out in the vastness of the digital world without any evidence or recording in either real or virtual space.

The digital economy is fueled by a voluminous amount of information and databases, which in turn raises the question not only of accounting, recording and storing data of personal consumption or financial transactions, but also the problem of protecting them from being used for personal gain and used in the shadow digital world. This question gives rise to the study of a completely new sector of the shadow economy and creates a fourth segment of the digital economy, which would ensure the safety of digital life.

Literature Review

The level of development of the system of economic, social and cultural relations based on the use of digital information and communication technologies determine the scale of digitization of the country's economy¹. According to scientific theorists, the concept of “digital economy” arose in the 90s of the twentieth century. In 1995, the ideology of the digital economy was best outlined by N. Negroponte² in his work entitled “The Transition from the Movement of

¹ Уринцов А. И. Некоторые вопросы формирования условий развития современной цифровой экономики / А. И. Уринцов, О. В. Староверова, Д. В. Галахов // Образование. Наука. Научные кадры. – 2017. – № 2. – С. 108-111. – EDN YLJRRB.

² Negroponte N. Being Digital. New York: Alfred A. Knopf 1995 Available at: <http://web.media.mit.edu/nicholas/Wired/WIRED3-02.html>

Atoms to the Movement of Bits.” The first decade of the twentieth century (since 1994) was aimed at the development of electronic commerce and services. Afterwards, the digital economy grew to another level of development: the service became more complex, disparate technologies began to be united. Today, the digital economy covers all spheres of life: healthcare, education, online banking, taxation and trade. Higher levels of development require breakthrough technologies in the IT field and more digital capabilities.

For the first time in 1994, the term “digital economy” was used by the author of the book “Electronic Digital Society” D. Tapscott³. List of scientists called D. Tapscott “one of the world's leading cyber gurus”⁴. A number of scientists note that there is no single term yet, and in addition to “digital economy”, in particular, the following are used: “electronic economy”, “new technological order of the world”, “API economy”, “application economy”, “creative economy” and etc⁵. In Europe, the term “digital economy” is often used, however, American companies represented by Deloitte, IBM and a number of others are inclined to use a more technological name – “API economy”.

Gartner⁶ has defined a new business model that embraces “everyone, everywhere, always” using information technology and the Internet on a global level, providing effective services, which are the main criteria for the digitalization of the business environment⁷. The integration of the Internet and innovative digital technologies of each individual of the economic system, including firms and states, is an integral stage of the digitalization of the economy.⁸ The fundamental and

³ Тапскотт Д. Электронно-цифровое общество. К.: «INT-press»; М.: «Релф-бук», 1999. — 432 с.

⁴ Ershova T.V., Yuri E. Hohlov and Sergei B. Shaposhnik, "Methodology for Digital Economy Development Assessment as a Tool for Managing the Digital Transformation Processes", in Management of large-scale system development: Proceedings of the 2018 Eleventh International Conference, MLSD 2018, Moscow, Russia, October 1-3, 2018. Electronic ISBN: 978-1-5386-4924-4; Print on Demand (PoD) ISBN: 978-1-5386-4925-1. DOI: 10.1109/MLSD.2018.8551846. IEEE, 2018. 1-3 p.

⁵ Калужный Е. Развитие цифровой экономики в России / Е. Калужный, Т. А. Кулакова, В. Н. Михайлов // Компьютерные технологии в моделировании, управлении и экономике: Сборник материалов IX-й международной научно-практической конференции, Орел, 09 марта 2017 года / Под общей редакцией А.В. Полянина. – Орел: Среднерусский институт управления - филиал РАНХиГС, 2017. – С. 215-217. – EDN ZRVCUJ.

⁶ <http://www.tadviser.ru/index.php/>

⁷ Добридюк С. Финтех и "диджитализация" банковской сферы. ГК «Диасофт». 2016. Доступно по: <https://www.slideshare.net/tribotinka/ss-63384661>

⁸ Izaret J., Sinha A. Game Changer: How Strategic Pricing Shapes Businesses, Markets, and Society. 2023. 1st ed. P.432

diversified transformation of the economy is due not only to information and communication technologies (ICT), but also to the investment potential of the state and business experts in the field of innovation in all sectors. Accordingly, as R. Atkinson noted, if you take a narrow and one-sided approach to the digitalization process, then you can only achieve the development of only one industry in the national economy.⁹

World Bank experts argue that “the digital economy is a new paradigm for accelerated economic development”, which is based on real-time data exchange.¹⁰ In addition, a number of experts argue that the most striking example of a successful digital transformation can be the formation of the “Uberization of the economy,” where successful innovations are not technological, but in the field of business models, where there is a large-scale, systemic and deeply thought-out level of transformation of the economy and society.¹¹

The experience of foreign countries in the field of digitalization of the economy deserves special attention. When assessing the level of development of the digital economy, ratings based on the level of digitalization of the economies of countries are important. Over the past years, China has been systematically moving toward the top spot in the digital environment. China overtook the United States and took a leadership position back in 2016. Since then, China has not only not slowed down its growth rate, but has also increased its activity aimed at universal digitalization. The country confidently holds first place in the number of patents actually received. For example, the US IT infrastructure is based mainly on investments from private enterprises and entrepreneurs, and government participation is modest. At the early stages of enterprises, the state helps their technological development. The government's main assistance is to help companies adapt through tax breaks, as companies can write off costs for servers, hardware,

⁹ Кто и как управляет развитием цифровой экономики. Tadviser 2020. Доступно по: <https://www.tadviser.ru/a/381753>

¹⁰ Уринцов А. И. Некоторые вопросы формирования условий развития современной цифровой экономики / А. И. Уринцов, О. В. Староверова, Д. В. Галахов // Образование. Наука. Научные кадры. – 2017. – № 2. – С. 108-111. – EDN YLJRRB.

¹¹ Maguer R. The 2021/2022 INSEAD Annual Report. 2022. Available at: <https://annual-report.insead.edu/homepage>

etc. One of the projects developed with government grants is Google. Although most of the money comes from private venture capital funds, the government directly assists in investment, where as they improve and develop, the market independently comes up with business models.

SWOT analysis

In revealing the advantages and disadvantages of digitalization on the path to the legalization of the shadow economy, taking into account the basic economic contradiction of interests of state institutions and private and family enterprises by providing them with freedom to operate on the Internet, we used the SWOT analysis method, which presents the following conclusions:

Strengths:

1. Increasing transparency. Digitalization allows for better tracking and recording of financial transactions, making it more difficult for businesses and individuals to engage in shadow economic activities without detection.

2. Simplification of access and analysis of data. Digital tools enable the collection and analysis of vast amounts of data that can be used to identify patterns and anomalies indicative of underground economy activity.

3. Increasing the efficiency of government bodies. Automation and digital processes simplify administrative tasks and reduce compliance burdens, making it easier for businesses to operate in the formal economy.

4. Elimination of the human factor. Digital platforms provide access to information and resources that can educate businesses and individuals about the benefits of participating in the formal economy, potentially encouraging compliance.

Weaknesses:

1. Digital gap. Not everyone has equal access to digital technologies, which can exacerbate existing inequalities and hinder efforts to reduce the shadow economy in regions with limited internet connectivity or technology infrastructure.

2. Cybersecurity risks. Digital systems are vulnerable to cyber attacks and data breaches that can compromise sensitive financial information and undermine trust in digital platforms used for economic transactions.

3. Cost. Implementing digital solutions can require significant upfront investments in technology infrastructure, software and training, which can be prohibitively expensive for small businesses or cash-based economies.

Opportunities:

1. Innovation. The continued development of digital technologies such as blockchain and artificial intelligence opens up new opportunities for developing more secure and efficient systems for tracking financial transactions and combating the shadow economy.

2. Cooperation. Public-private partnerships and international collaboration can facilitate the sharing of best practices and resources to leverage digitalization to reduce the shadow economy globally.

3. Education and awareness. Digital platforms can be used to disseminate information and cultivate generations with a high level of social conscience and intolerance towards TE, raising awareness of the negative consequences of participation in the underground economy, as well as the benefits of formalization.

4. Regulatory approval. Governments can use digitalization to streamline regulatory processes and reduce bureaucratic barriers to formal economic participation, making it more attractive for businesses and individuals to comply with tax and labor laws.

Threats:

1. Adaptation of the shadow economy. As digital technologies evolve, the strategies and tactics used by shadow economy actors to circumvent detection and enforcement efforts may evolve, creating a continuing challenge for regulators and law enforcement.

2. Privacy issues. Large-scale collection and analysis of digital data raises concerns about privacy rights and potential abuses of surveillance powers by

governments and corporations, which could undermine public confidence in digitalization initiatives aimed at reducing the shadow economy.

3. Over-regulation: Over-regulation and oversight in the name of combating the shadow economy can stifle innovation, limit economic freedom, and disproportionately burden legitimate businesses and individuals without effectively addressing the root causes of informal economic activity.

Digitalization level of Uzbekistan

According to a study by the non-governmental human rights organization Freedom House, Uzbekistan took 57th place in the Internet freedom ranking, where researchers analyzed the situation in 65 countries. The report is based on data received from June 1, 2019 to May 31, 2020.¹² This rating was compiled based on three priority factors: obstacles to Internet access, content restrictions and violation of user rights. The lower the score in the ranking, the stricter the Internet regulation in the country is considered. Data published by Infocom.uz, where at the beginning of 2018 the total number of Internet users in our country was 20 million and increased over the year by 5.3 million users (an increase of 36%). At the same time, the total speed of Uzbekistan's access to international networks was 104.1 Gbit/s, and the growth of this indicator over the year was more than 58%.¹³

The Ministry of Information and Communications has published data on the total length of fiber-optic communication lines in Uzbekistan, which at the beginning of 2018 is 22.35 thousand kilometers. Of these, more than 2 thousand kilometers were built in 2017 alone. According to the data from government information services, it is worth noting that an improvement in the quality of the Internet and an increase in the number of users has been observed over the past 3-4 years, but this does not indicate the deterritorialization and prevalence of Internet users, since the indicators are aggregated.

¹² Overview Uzbekistan. Key Developments, June 1, 2018-May 31, 2019. Freedom House. 2020. Available at: <https://freedomhouse.org/country/uzbekistan/freedom-net/2019>

¹³ Infocom.uz 2020. Динамика пропускной способности международной сети передачи данных (гбит/сек) в Узбекистане.

Figure 2. Number of Internet users in Central Asian countries. (in percentages)¹⁴

In the global ranking of Cable.co.uk, according to data by the beginning of 2023 on the cost of broadband Internet access, Uzbekistan’s position is among the cheapest in the region of 0.23-30 US dollars per month and has risen to 131st place (24 lines to the top) Worldwide broadband speed league 2023. Among the countries of Central Asia, Uzbekistan ranks second after Kazakhstan in terms of the number of Internet users (with a difference of 25%). (Fig. 2.) In addition, let us pay attention to the position of Uzbekistan in international digital and ICT ratings. The picture of Uzbekistan in this regard is such that digitalization indicators are reflected in the following key international digital and ICT ratings in the period 2016-2023. According to the E-Government Index in 2022, Uzbekistan’s position has improved significantly and took 69th place. Growth is also observed in the Global Innovation Index ranking by 4 positions among the same 193 countries.

Methodology

The study examines the variables “number of internet users” named “intuse” that indicated as a proxy for the digitalization and takes part from regression analysis as an independent variable. Dependent variable is the share of shadow economy (“shek”) from the official economics measured in GDP. Estimations are made from the Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dataset that includes time period from 2005 to 2022 with the implementation of

¹⁴ Всемирный банк. Оценка объема теневой экономики Узбекистана, Региональная перспектива. 2020г

Vector Error Correction (VEC) model as we have stochastic time series data and examining the long-term relationship of two variables.

Estimation Results

In this study, the results of VEC regression model revealed that a 1% change in second-order Internet use is associated with a second-order change in the shadow economy of -8.99885%. In the regression, the second category of indicators was used since when testing this with the Dickey-Fuller test, it was revealed that the date is not stationary (Table 1.).

Table 1. Regression analysis of the influence of the number of Internet users (intuse) on the share of the shadow economy, calculated using the Kagan method (shek).¹⁵

Variables	(1) D2.shek
D2.intuse	-8.999*** (2.252)
Const	2.112 (4.432)
Observations	17
R-squared	0.516

Standard errors in parentheses, *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The results of the calculation using the VEC method showed that the relationship between the two indicators has a long-term effect, which suggests that an increase in the number of Internet users does not immediately affect the decrease in the share of the shadow sector.

Conclusion

In conclusion, to one degree or another, it can be argued that the digitalization of the economy and the automation of other processes in economic sectors can provide serious resistance to the growth of the shadow economy. In order to legalize the shadow economy, it is necessary to empirically study the shadow economy and trends in the development of digitalization. The above-mentioned

¹⁵ Compiled by the author

and used dependent variable is estimated by method for determining the share of the shadow economy involve calculations based on the cash supply of money, since it is the digitalization of the economy that will serve to transfer transactions in many areas of activity into electronic ones. For example, in Uzbekistan, the first steps have already been taken towards the digitalization of a certain money supply since the spring of 2020; pensions and salaries of employees of budgetary organizations have been transferred to a non-cash form of payment.

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